

ABSTRACT BOOK

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COMORBIDITY OF CHRONIC PAIN AND MENTAL
HEALTH DISORDERS: BREAKING THE CYCLE

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II-C.05**PAIN MONITORING WITH ENTROPY MODULE DURING UROLOGICAL SURGERY**R. Marinova¹, K. Tsvetanova²¹UMHAT Alexandrovska, Sofia, Bulgaria, ²Medical University Pleven, Pleven, Bulgaria

Background and aims: The problem with antinociception during general anesthesia is complicated considering the great interindividual differences in opioid consumption. Standard signs for adequate intraoperative analgesia could not be reliable due to type of surgery, condition of the patient etc.. Potential objective information may be taken from EMG activity of facial muscles during surgical stimulation. Such an index is entropy, calculated from mathematical analysis of EEG and the difference RE (response entropy 0-47Hz) – SE (state entropy 0-32Hz).

The aim of the study is to explore the role of entropy monitoring for opioid consumption and recovery from anesthesia.

Methods: The study was held in 43 patients who underwent urological surgery. Patients were ASA III, Lee score ≥ 3 .

General anesthesia was maintained with Sevoflurane and Sufentanil.

In Group A (n=22) - RE-SE entropy was monitored, in group B (n=23) – only standard signs for analgesia.

The total dose of Sufentanil, time for spontaneous breathing recovery (SBR), obeying to verbal command (OBC), VAS after extubation, frequency of adverse effects were recorded.

Results: The total dose of Sufentanil was lower in group A (20 ± 6 mcg), compared to group B (30 ± 3 mcg), SVR was 7 ± 4 min in group A and 12 ± 6 min in group B, OVC was 12 ± 3 min in group A and 16 ± 2 min in group B. VAS and adverse events were comparable into two groups.

Conclusions: Entropy monitoring during anesthesia leads to less opioid consumption and faster recovery after anesthesia. Entropy RE-SE difference could be used for intraoperative analgesia monitoring.

II-C.06**TEST-RETEST RELIABILITY OF VON FREY FILAMENT'S INDUCED TEMPORAL SUMMATION IN A HEALTHY POPULATION**A. Knezevic^{1,2}, T. Aleksandric^{1,2}, L. Vojnovic^{1,2}, E. Garipi^{1,2}, D. Popovic^{1,2}, T. Spasojevic^{1,2}, A. Savic^{1,2}¹Faculty of Medicine University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia, ²Medical Rehabilitation Clinic, University Clinical Center of Vojvodina, Novi Sad, Serbia

Background and aims: Data from the literature concerning the test-retest reliability of the temporal summation (TS) are still inconclusive. The aim of this study was to evaluate test-retest reliability of TS in healthy subjects and to determine whether there are differences between the sexes.

Methods: The phenomenon of temporal summation was examined with the help of Von Frey filaments (300g). Pain intensity (from 0-100) was recorded after the first and 10th prick. The difference in pain intensity after the 10th and after the 1st prick was considered a temporal summation (TS). Trials were performed on the dorsum of the hand, the ipsilateral pectoral area and the contralateral dorsum of the foot. A week later, a retest was conducted to assess the reliability of the previously mentioned testing protocol.

Results: Our study included 115 subjects (average age $27,6 \pm 6,13$ years, 61 women and 54 men). Men were significantly older ($30,5 \pm 5,8$ vs $25 \pm 5,2$; $t=5,4$, $p=0,000$). Retest evaluation of TS showed excellent reliability: the best was obtained for pectoral region (ICC=0,866, 95%CI 0,807-0,908), then for the hand dorsum (ICC=0,828, 95%CI 0,751-0,881) and dorsum of the foot (ICC=0,811, 95%CI 0,726-0,869). Better reliability was observed in men for the foot (ICC=0,849, 95%CI 0,739-0,912 vs ICC=0,786, 95%CI 0,645-0,871) and hand dorsum (ICC=0,841, 95%CI 0,725-0,908 vs ICC=0,814, 95%CI 0,691-0,889), while for pectoral region it was better in women (ICC=0,885, 95%CI 0,808-0,931 vs ICC=0,836, 95%CI 0,719-0,905).

Conclusions: In a healthy population, TS can be reliably induced utilizing the Von Frey filament (300g). Even though men were significantly older, they showed better test-retest reliability of TS for extremities.